

Due Diligence Report

The purpose of this report is to present the business plan, market analysis and innovative aspects of the proposed technology to investors. It has been prepared by the Cloud Walker team under the supervision of Prof. Tordella in collaboration with the Technology Transfer Office (RIMIN) and the Tech Incubator (I3P) of the Politecnico di Torino.

PROJECT/COMPANY NAME	CLOUD WALKER
RESEARCH INSTITUTE	POLITECNICO DI TORINO
REFERENT	DANIELA TORDELLA, DISAT, POLITECNICO di TORINO
WEBSITE	n.a.
STAGE	Tech incubation
TRL	5
TECH4PLANET READINESS LEVEL	[TBD]

0. INTRODUCTION AND INNOVATIVE ASPECTS

The hydrological cycle of the Earth is the sum total of all processes in which water moves from the land and ocean surface to the atmosphere and back in form of precipitation. It allows life on Earth. Understanding the role of clouds and of their formation/decay processes, which are not yet fully known inside Earth's atmosphere, helps to understand and control the process of water precipitation and its relevant surface distribution. CLOUD WALKER is an innovative method of observation based on clusters of newly designed mini green radiosondes able to endoscopically measure the fluctuations of physical-chemical quantities present inside and outside both atmospheric clouds and anthropogenic environmental clouds residing over urban and/or industrial sites. The duration of the observation is of the order of 2-3 hours and is spread over spatial volumes of the order of 10^3 Km^3 . The CLOUD WALKER associated receiver system performs data acquisition and post-processing. CLOUD WALKER also offers a platform for multiple radiosonde data acquisition, management and post-processing.

1. TEAM: COMPOSITION, CHARACTERISTICS AND COMMENTS

The team involved in the project is part of the **Dipartimento di Scienza Applicata** and of the **Dipartimento di Elettronica e Telecomunicazioni** del **Politecnico di Torino**. The team that will work on the development of the *proof of concept (POC)* is the following:

Daniela Tordella (Chief Scientific Advisor, Part time 40%, however, full time option is not excluded and will be defined during the Tech incubation activities):

Associate Professor POLITO, DISAT. Expert in turbulent transport and mixing, hydrodynamical stability of wakes and channel flows, solar wind outer heliosphere spectral analysis, and Young Stellar Objects

jets simulation in the laboratory. She managed several research projects at national and international level: EU as PI and US as co-PI (NASA). Proponent and Principal investigator of CLOUD WALKER related granted projects: H2020-MSCA ITN ETN COMPLETE and POC-MIGRE (Links FOUNDATION, CSP).

She has obtained more than 20 national and international projects for funding exceeding 6€M. She is the author of more than 200 peer-reviewed publications.

PoC role & Commitment. Chief Scientific Officer (CSO): Since 2015, guidance for the process flow of the CLOUD WALKER project and parent previous projects: conceptualization, development of the working method, performing experiments and analyses, in particular organization and implementation of the in-field testing campaign, development and deployment of the relevant software, proposal writing, fund acquisition on a competitive basis, maintenance and care of the international and national relations with potential stakeholders and customers.

Type of contract: Associate Professor

Contract expiration date: permanent

Eros Pasero (Scientific Advisor, Part-time at 40%):

Associate Professor at DET, POLITO, at Tongji University (24/3/2017-20/4/2017), (1/3/2015-8/4/2015) and at Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent (2012-2014).

Prof. Pasero is Italian member of SIRWEC (Standing International Road Weather Commission) and the co-founder of SIREN, the Italian Society for Neural Networks. He holds 5 international patents, two of which have been the first silicon European neurons and synapse developed with Texas Instruments. He was the founder of N-Lab, one of the first spin-off of Politecnico di Torino. He was the scientific coordinator of several European and Italian research projects and of different PoC funded projects. IEEE Distinguished Lecturer I&M society (2021-)

PoC role & Commitment. Scientific Advisor. Electronics design supervisor. Principal responsible for the process flow on the development of electronics and remote sensing technologies.

Type of contract: Associate Professor

Contract expiration date: permanent

Vincenzo Randazzo (CEO, full time)

RTD-A Research fellow at DET, POLITO.

He holds a Ph.D. cum laude in Electrical, Electronics and Communications Engineering with a thesis on machine learning. He got a research grant on "Technology transfer: prototyping and business development activities in entrepreneurship start-up programs", where he worked as mentor for several Innovation programs.

He has two Italian patents in his portfolio as inventor. He was CEO of SoundBubble startup, a spinoff of Politecnico di Torino. He was part of different PoC funded projects.

PoC role & Commitment. CEO. Business developer, Data scientist Machine learning expert for data processing, Hardware development supervisor

Type of contract: Research fellow (RTD-A)

Contract expiration date: fixed-term contract, February 2025

Shahbozbek Abdunabiev. (CTO, full time)

PHD candidate at DET, Research assistant at DISAT, POLITO. Since 2020 he participated to the development cycle (design, testing, firmware development, data-acquisition and post-processing) of the radiosonde board. Worked as backend software developer at Wing.ae (Dubai, UAE) startup company.

PoC role & Commitment. CTO. Project manager undertaking to seek, develop, and validate the Cloud Walker project. Technology developer, directly contributing to the hardware and software (firmware, data acquisition) development.

Type of contract: Assegnista di Ricerca Universitario.

Contract expiration date: fixed-term contract, January 2024.

Team contacts: daniela.tordella@polito.it, referent for the project; eros.pasero@polito.it, vincenzo.randazzo@polito.it, shahbozbek.abdunabiev@polito.it.

In the case of the establishment of a spin-off company, the team foresees the possibility to hire some additional figures, specifically selected for the company management, and for sales and marketing functions.

Cap table

The team proposes a preliminary distribution of the shares as indicated below, the cap table will be finalized during the POC activities.

It is agreed that **TECH4PLANET fund** will join the initial equity distribution with a share of 10%

Shares: Daniela Tordella 40%, Eros Pasero 20%, Vincenzo Randazzo 25%, Shahbozbek Abdunabiev 5% (pending conditions on VISA, EU and National legislations). In light of a future spin-off, the establishment of an **employee stock option pool** will be considered. .

Impact on future leadership. By hiring a number of young technologists (44% of female participation target as required by European Gender Equality Plan), CLOUD WALKER will contribute in increasing the number of young STEM people in the multidisciplinary environment technologies. Individually tailored career development plans will be offered.

General comment

- The team is very experienced on the topic and has all the skills required to complete the product and business development of the project.
- The team is mostly made up of seniors who hold well-established positions in Academia; in case a spin-off is created, two members of the team will work full-time in the company.
- In case of a spin-off, people with technical expertise in renewable industry and transport must be hired.

2. TECHNOLOGY: DESCRIPTION, CHARACTERISTICS, DEFENSIBILITY

The aim of **Cloud Walker** is to develop a **new in-field measurement system** based on innovative mini **green** radiosonde, able to reside within the clouds floating passively inside them at different altitudes for long times, 2-3 hours, and over large spaces, of the order of 10^3 km^2 . In current technologies, probes are either **fixed** on the ground or traverse the atmosphere as a **sounding** system, by ascending the atmosphere under buoyancy forces, or, as a **dropsonde**, essentially a radiosonde that is released from specially equipped aircraft and descends to the surface by parachute, see figure 1 below. In these cases, it is not certain that the ascending or descending trajectories pass through cloud formations, but even if this were the case, the crossing is very fast, lasting one-two minutes, which does not allow us **endoscopic observations**. In particular, the observation of the **spectra of the intense internal fluctuations** (the analog of the "electrocardiogram") that characterize the life cycle of the clouds, both atmospheric or anthropogenic. Conversely to current technologies, Cloud Walker radiosondes weights **less than 20 g** and employs a small (**less than 30 cm in diameter**) **biodegradable balloon**.

A • fixed point measurement stations

B • probes (dropsonde) crossing the atmosphere under **gravitational free fall**

C • quickly profiling entire atmosphere by buoyancy, Helium filled large balloons

FIG. 1 - CURRENT TECHNOLOGIES, AVERAGE WEIGHT: B DROPSONDE 300 G, C 600 G

Improving the understanding of clouds means improving climate and environmental monitoring at large, with all the related ecological, biological, social and economic consequences.

Achievement of the Free Flotation Requisite (passive transport). The innovation of Cloud Walker, developed within the H2020-COMLETE www.complete-h2020network.eu and POC-MIGRE projects, is the **capability of freely floating** (a feature called passive transport) **inside clouds without substantially perturbing them**. This was obtained by implementing the criterion of minimization of weight and size of the prototype. Because of these features, by both European and National legislation, **Cloud Walker, as birds, does not require a permit of flight**. On the contrary, the use of drones, airplanes, or similar, alters clouds and, therefore, all the measurements are badly affected. Furthermore, such an active transport introduces unavoidable high level of electrical and mechanical noise on the Printed Circuit Board **PCB** transceiver signals (both the transmitted and received ones).

The proposed measurement system will be used in high-potential, **technical and industrial/environmental-clima applications** (in various fields: scientific, environmental monitoring of city areas, alpine valleys, agriculture crops, hazardous events like wildfires, volcanic eruptions, etc...).

Fig. 2 - Cloud Walker tracks the turbulent fluctuations of air velocity and acceleration, water vapor concentration, liquid droplets and aerosol concentration (VOC, volatile, or semi-volatile, organic compounds), temperature, pressure and atmospheric magnetic field.

Measurement System Architecture:

The working principle of the measurement system is based on the Wireless Sensor Network (WSN). This WSN is structured in three main parts: the **radioprobe** attached to the **biodegradable balloon**, which includes the solid-state sensors to measure the physical quantities of interest, and it transmits the collected and pre-processed data to the ground; **the receiver stations**, which receive, store, and pass this information to the processing machine; and **the processing machine**, which process and manage data monitoring, and visualization.

The radio communication system of the radioprobes enables the one-way wireless communication with ground stations using radiofrequency signals. Because of its **low-power/long-range** features and proper architecture and implementation, LoRa communication technology has been adopted. The tests of the radio transmission protocol were made using a programmed output power of 10 dBm, central frequency 865.2 MHz (ISM frequency available in Europe), spreading factor of 10, and a bandwidth of 125 (250, 500) kHz. All parameters comply with the regulations released by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute.

Advantages of the new solution.

- **Low cost/Expendability:** important for environmental monitoring by local governmental institution, by industrial companies included in the National Inventory of Plants at Risk of Major Accident (European Directive III Seveso); important when clusters of order 100 elements are used by National Centres for Atmospheric Research to carry out fluctuation measurements inside cumulus clouds
- On the contrary of what done by fixed observation stations or vertical atmospheric profiles obtained via LIDARs, and conventional radiosonde (e.g. Vaisala or GRAW), **the ability to passively float** (wandering around as a **single** element or as a **cluster** of elements) inside extended portions (**decades of kilometers**) of atmospheric layers at various altitudes and to track continuously in time and space, multiphase and multiscale motions and various kind of aerosols (as gaseous, liquid or solid pollutants)
- At lower altitudes (up to 200-300 meters of altitude), the **spatial and long-lasting temporal wandering** of Cloud Walker radiosonde allows for a very efficient monitoring in urban areas.
- **Lightweight:** total weight **less than 20 grams**, including the printed circuit board PCB, the outer shell and supports.
- **Compact size:** board size is actually 4 x 3.5 cm, the balloon 30 cm in diameter.
- **Accurate positioning data** (~2-3 meters). Existing radiosondes only use GNSS based positioning (~8-10 meters), while we integrated IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) together with GNSS to improve positioning.
- **Low power consumption.**

General comment

- **NOVAMONT MATER BI® Biodegradable Balloons:** this feature is a first implementation worldwide. As a consequence, the proposed mini radiosonde constitutes an advanced technology with a potentially positive effect on the environment, metropolitan areas and people's life.
- As the first basic proof of concept has already been successfully completed, the main challenge resides in the optimization of the technology and its test in an operational environment.
- Aside the advantages listed above, the DEFENSIBILITY is associated to the new methodology of use that CLOUD WALKER proposes with respect to current technologies (instrumentation and measurement techniques).

3. MARKET: APPLICATIONS, POTENTIAL MARKET, COMPETITIVE CONTEXT, MARKET STANDARD

Cloud Walker will vastly improve Europe's position as a global leader in technology, science and innovation to address climate change challenge and all related contexts.

MARKET ANALYSIS

The Cloud Walker's system can provide techniques to analyze physical and chemical processes inside clouds (or other atmospheric environments) and can generate a dataset that can significantly improve our understanding of clouds as well as the weather prediction, atmospheric parameter and climate simulation models. Better atmospheric and environmental inspection bring benefits and optimize decision making in both economy and society (early warning, post-event analysis...).

The Earth Observation will be the reference market: it comprehends remote sensing and in-situ technologies used to capture the planet's physical, chemical, and biological systems and to monitor land, water and the atmosphere. According to information in the EO market report (EUSPA - European Union Agency for the Space Programme, 2022) the total revenues for data and value-added services in this market amounted to €2,8 bn in 2021, divided as in the figure below:

Distribution of revenue by segments (€m, 2021)

The expected CAGR is 6,8% in the next decade that led to €4.7 bn total revenues by 2031.

The technology can be applied in different market segments: agriculture, climate services, emergency management and humanitarian aid, environmental monitoring and urban development. The value of these markets will amount to €1,8 bn in 2027.

The target customers can be both platform providers (that will purchase raw and post processing data) and EO products and services providers (that will be interested in the platform system).

The interested parties may be:

National and international research centers, such as Thematic Exploitation Platform (ESA), CNR, CNRS, Max Planck Institute, NCAR, NOAA, Riken, or Universities Laboratories.

Urban area monitoring: National, Regional, City level (Local) monitoring structures (e.g. Environment Protection, and Smart-City applications).

Prevention, rescue relief services: Institutional agency for fire and rescue service, such as ATM-PRO Belgium,

Meteoblue AG CH, Scintec AG Germany, Lakes Environmental Software Canada, Environmodeling Ltd. Chile, IES Solutions srl. Italy, Air Water Noise Consultant Australia, Enivitech Europe Ltd UK.

Industrial safety: companies exposed to major-accident hazards that need to check for possible upgrading and adjustment of their facilities; in Europe there are more than 12.000 industries involved, among them over 1.000 are in Italy

In the table below are considered the specific use cases for Cloud Walker:

	Long / short weather forecasting	Climate monitoring	Air quality monitoring and Urban heat islands	Early warning and post-event analysis	Impact studies	Monitoring of ESG policies
Science		✓			✓	
Urban monitoring	✓		✓			✓
Prevention and rescue services	✓	✓		✓		
Industrial safety			✓			✓

These activities accounted for €479 mln, and will increase to €665 mln by 2027.

Business applications can be found in four main areas:

1. Science: cloud microphysics and dynamics in field observation. Potential clients are the national and international research centers, such as ESA, NASA, CNR, CNRS, Max Planck Institute, NCAR, NOAA, Riken, or Universities Laboratories. Considering only VAISALA, one of the biggest radiosonde manufacturers, it declared around 255 M€ net sales in 2021 for weather and environment business area. Indeed, each day around 1400 VAISALA radiosondes are launched, which accounts for around 500K in one year and involves a **dispersion of 420 kg of non-biodegradable latex, i.e. 150 tons per year.**
2. Urban area monitoring: National, Regional, City level (Local) monitoring structures (e.g. Environment Protection, and Smart-City applications). In Italy, ARPA (Regional Agency for Environmental Protection) agencies and Italian Aeronautics launch around 5000 radiosondes each year, which accounts for around 1.5M€ expenditure plus the cost of the base station, the helium, and trained personnel.
3. Prevention, rescue relief services: Institutional agency for fire and rescue service, such as ATM-PRO Belgium, Meteoblue AG CH, Scintec AG Germany, Lakes Environmental Software Canada, Environmodeling Ltd. Chile, IES Solutions srl. Italy, Air Water Noise Consultant Australia, Enivitech Europe Ltd UK.
4. Industrial safety (**SEVESO directive**).

In summary the TAM is the total value of the market segments inherent to Cloud Walker technology, the SAM represents the portion of the TAM in which the technology is exploitable.

Considering the market assumptions and the innovative improvement that Cloud Walker brings to the market the Serviceable Obtainable Market is around € 13M at the 5th year. The figure shows the projected amounts over the next 5 years:

INDUSTRY ANALYSIS

The EO value chain is presented in the figure below.

The industry is split into four categories namely, Data acquisition and distribution, Data processing, and Analysis, insights, decision support and end users. Cloud Walker can be seen as a platform for data management and post processing, that allow to offer:

- Data acquisition (radiosonde, for aerosol/chemical monitoring inside and outside atmospheric cloud)
- Post processing data
- Raw Data

Considering such different products that can be offered, Cloud Walker is positioned upstream in the value chain: it deals with data acquisition distribution and processing.

The table below shows the main industry players divided according to their positioning in the value chain.

Top 10 companies across the value chain based on 2019 revenues

Data acquisition and distribution	Data processing	Analysis, insights & decision support	Users
Maxar	US Maxar	US Airbus	NL
Airbus	NL Airbus	NL Leonardo	IT
Thales	FR Alphabet Inc. (Google)	US Verisk	US
Planet	US Leonardo	IT Trimble Inc.	US
Leonardo	IT Oracle Corp	US NEC Corporation	JP
Amazon	US Amazon	US CGI Inc.	CA
Space Imaging Middle East	AE CGI Inc.	CA Maxar	US
21AT	CN ESRI	US VITO	BE
KSAT	NO Trimble	US 21AT	CN
Science and Technology Holding B.V.	NL Cyient Limited	IN Beijing Piesat	CN

The top companies tend to differ across the value chain. However, big companies such as Maxar, Airbus and Amazon have presence in more than one value chain category. In this scenario, Cloud walker fits the first two columns on the left and his clients will be the EO products and service providers.

POLICY MAKERS

One of the main programmes in Europe is the “European Union’s Earth Observation and Monitoring programme”, known as Copernicus. It offers information services that draw from EO data. Copernicus delivers accurate information services, draw from EO data, in the field of environment and security; supports a wide range of Union policies in domains such as agriculture, environment, energy, health, civil protection, humanitarian aid and transport. Mainly tailored to the needs of public authorities, Copernicus also serves research, academic, commercial and other private users.

Other important policies are contained in the European Green Deal: a package of initiatives presented by the EU in 2019 as a central part of the EU strategy to implement the United Nation’s 2030 Agenda and its sustainable development goals. It aims to build a new and green economic model which will transform Europe in the first climate-neutral continent by 2050.

The Seveso Directive, concerning more than 12.000 industry in Europe, aims to control major accident hazards involving dangerous substances, especially chemicals and contributes to the technological disaster risk reduction effort. The Directive is widely considered as a benchmark for industrial accident policy and has been a role model for legislation in many countries world-wide.

Business model

Cloud Walker can be framed as both a **B2G** and a **B2B** solution. Cloud Walker can be considered both a hardware and a software company, which means it produces and sells radioprobes but, also, raw and structured data.

As explained in the previous section the go-to-market strategy foresees to first tackle the **B2G** business of environment/climate monitoring, either directing to **International** (World Wide) and **European research institution or**

local governmental institution, and, then, tackle the **B2B** business for local pollutant and dangerous substances monitoring.

Market standard and competition

Radiosondes and dropsondes are common instrumentation used for atmospheric measurements, especially for vertical profiling and **upper-air** (low, medium and high altitude) measurements. Radiosondes from various manufacturers share similar features, such as: Data transmission via **radio** modulation by using specific bandwidth (**403 MHz, 865 MHz, 1680 Mhz**, etc.); Sensing **PTU** (pressure, temperature, humidity) information and sending them via radio; Sonde position is tracked with on of the following techniques: **radar, radio signal strength and GPS**, etc. However, position accuracy depends on the data transmission rate, post- processing and technology used; **Vertical profiling** measurements of the atmosphere up to 30000 meters of altitude.

Cloud-Walker radiosonde provides abovementioned features **together with custom features, such as:**

- **Cluster of radiosondes:** Wireless sensor network architecture allows to use radiosondes in clusters
- **Passive Floating, monitoring and residence inside over cloud's lifespan:** The radiosonde can follow passively fluid/gas/air flow around it and stay inside atmosphere, Clouds and industrial or accidental plumes (e.g., toxic and radioactive substances) for a long period of time.
- **Small Scale Lagrangian fluctuations tracking:** Tracking small variations of physical quantities, such as position, velocity, acceleration, humidity, pressure and temperature.
- **Turbulent mechanical energy and dispersion tracking:** Quantification of Turbulent mechanical energy intensity and Dispersion inside Atmosphere and Cloud
- **Hazardous chemical and particle detection:** Detection of particulate and hazardous airborne chemicals
- **Green Balloons:** Balloons are biodegradable.
- **Small size, low weight:** radiosonde electronic board should be designed and produced as small as possible thus limiting the resulting **electronic waste** entering the environment.

The table below lists the most known radiosonde producer companies:

NOTE: indicates Yes, on-demand, requires customization

Features Company	Proposed Technology	Cluster of radiosondes	Passive Floating, monitoring and residence inside over cloud's lifespan	Vertical atmospheric profiling	Small Scale Lagrangian fluctuations tracking	Turbulent mechanical energy and dispersion tracking	Hazardous chemical and particle detection	Green Balloons	Weight and Dimension of radiosonde: 1- radioprobe and 2- balloon
Cloud Walker, Italy (OUR SYSTEM)	Radiosonde Balloons, Receiver, software, Post-processing (optional)		1: 10 gr, 3.5 x 4.5 cm 2: 10 gr, 15 cm radius						
Meteolabor AG, Switzerland	radiosonde: balloons, drone, airplane to be supplied		1: 200 gr, 22 x 11 x 8 cm 2: 200 gr, 1.1 meters (smallest)						
Yankee Environmental Systems, USA	Radiosondes, ground launching and monitoring stations, radiometers, sensors and software solutions		1: 100 gr (without battery), 20 x 10 x 10 cm 2: 200 gr, 1.1 meters (smallest)						
Vaisala, Finland	Radiosondes, ground stations, sounding systems and stations, radars, lidars, data loggers, sensors, monitoring, modeling and post-processing software solutions		1: 80 gr (without cover), 15.5x6.3x4.6 cm 2: 200-600 gr, 1.1 meters						

GRAW Radiosonde GmbH & Co. KG, Germany	Radiosondes, ground stations, antennas, software solutions, cloud based data storage	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	1: 63 gr, 9 x 6.7 x 4.4 cm 2: 200 gr, 1.1 meters (smallest)
Meteo modem, France	Sensors, dropsonde, pilotesonde, radars, ground stations	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	1: 36 gr, 9.8 x 6.3 x 4.2 cm 2: 200 gr, 1.1 meters (smallest)
Sparv Embedded AB, Sweden	Radiosondes, sensors for UAV, receiver stations	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	1: 16 gr, 2: 10 gr, 30-40 cm
InterMet Systems, Inc. USA	Radiosonde, sensors, ground stations, sounding systems, balloons, parachutes	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	1: 120 gr, 23.5 x 7.0 x 3.0 cm 2: 200 gr, 1.1 meters (smallest)
Liberty International	Ozonesondes, receiver stations, ozonizers and ozonometers	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	1: 240-480 gr 7.6 x 7.9 x 13.3 cm 2: 200-600 gr, 1.1 meters

In the following table, we list **additional companies that work with software solutions, ground stations, sensor and balloon production. Software solutions, sensors and balloon production, and sounding systems:**

Features	Proposed Technology	Data acquisition system	Post-processing toolbox	Weather, particle detection sensors	Green Balloons
Company					
Cloud Walker, Italy (OUR SYSTEM)	Radiosonde Balloons, Receiver, software, Post-processing (optional)	✓	✓	✓	✓
Pawan Exports, India	Balloons, parachutes, sensors, data loggers, ground stations	✓	✗	✓	✗
Lakes Environmental Software, Canada	software modeling		✓	✗	✗
Innovative Sensor Tech. AG, USA	Humidity sensor design and production	✗	✗	✓	✗
Jinyang Industrial Co, Ltd., South Korea	Sensors, data loggers	✓	✗	✓	✗
Aero-Laser GmbH, Germany	Laser measurement sensors and station	✓	✗	✓	✗
Coastal Environmental Systems, Inc., USA	Ground and portable weather stations, radars, software solutions	✓	✓	✓	✗
Felix Technology Inc., Canada	Telemetry, sounding stations, sensors, weather stations, balloons	✓	✓	✓	✗
Earth Resources Tech. Inc., USA	Remote sensing algorithms, software solutions and consultancy, instrumentation calibration services	✗	✓	✗	✗
Wittich & Visser, Netherlands	Sensors, weather stations, radars, sodars	✓	✗	✓	✗
Radiometric Corporation, USA	Radars, sodars, sounding systems, weather forecasting software	✓	✓	✗	✗

General comment

- The platform can be considered a replacement for several mobility instruments and gives a relevant contribution to the 2050 target of zero net emissions.
- The absence of equivalent technologies on the market, although desired, expresses the challenges in their development, which require very specific and technical know-how.

4. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY: BACKGROUND IP

Patent: Title: Radiosonda atmosferica e metodo per il suo funzionamento Priority date: *May 19, 2022*

Priority number: 102022000010403, Ownership:

Politecnico di Torino (100%)

Inventors: Eros Gian Alessandro Pasero, Vincenzo Randazzo, Daniela Tordella, Marco Allegretti, Miryam Elizabeth Paredes Quintanilla, Shahbozbek Abdunabiev

Status: *Italian patent-pending (Priority Period).*

In May 2023, we will submit the request for PCT extension.

5. PROOF OF CONCEPT: POC CHARACTERISTICS, FEASIBILITY AND TIMELINE

The POC will focus on the development and production of a functional prototype of the CLOUD WALKER radiosonde system and will last **18 months**. The plan includes 7 work packages (WPs), broken down into tasks. Each WP time span is reported below and expressed in months.

The technology has been tested in the laboratories and in various kinds of environmental and Alpine Valley in-fields tests: tethered mono-probe, tethered multi-probes, freely floating small swarm of 10 probes. The current TRL is 5 and by the end of the POC, the expected final TRL will be 7 (meaning that the prototype will be demonstrated in an operational environment). The activities carried out in the POC project will be mainly aimed at testing the technology in the operational environment.

Current prototype - TRL 5

H2020 ITN- COMPLETE (3.6 M€)
PoC- MIGRE (50 k€)

1st (red) and 2nd (green) prototype of the radiosonde board.

FIG. 3

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

With the Tech4Planet POC, we intend to reach a **TRL 7** by means of:

- **Developing a commercial production process** of the measurement system.
- We would like to provide **our product as a bundle**, made of:
 - Radiosondes (biodegradable balloon, radioprobe hardware and firmware). At least two radiosondes will be included in each set to allow an analysis of pair dispersion and pair correlation of physical quantities.
 - Receiver stations (hardware and software). At least one receiver will be required to use the system.

- Data acquisition, monitoring and innovative post-processing system (software, installations, and usage manuals). Most of it has already been developed in the previous funded projects.
- **Finding initial customers** for the first commercial product package.
- Getting ready for the **launch of the start-up**.

The final outcome of the POC project will be a **working prototype of the CLOUD WALKER** mini green expendable radiosonde with a complete and qualified system tested in an operational environment.

WORK PACKAGES

WP1: Business planning & Market definition

TEAM + i3P incubator at POLITO:

T1.1 Write the overall Business plan

T1.2 Define the list of actions

T1.3 Define the marketing strategy.

WP2: In-field testing campaign (Market validation)

TEAM + POLITO Borsa di Ricerca wp3-wp4-wp5 grantees

T2.1 Mini radiosonde in-field testing campaign with international academic institutions: **T2.1.1** NCAR Boulder US, Dr. Wojciech Grabowski, **T2.1.2** METOFFICE Reading UK, Dr. Kalli Furtado, **T2.1.3** MAX PLANK- University of Warsaw, Prof. Szymon Malinowski)

T2.2 Mini radiosonde in-field testing campaign with national and regional Italian governmental institution: INRIM CNR, ARPA Piemonte e Valle d'Aosta, Regione Piemonte

WP3: Data acquisition and management. Software further development

TEAM + wp3 POLITO Borsa di Ricerca grantee

T3.1 Software further development multichannel fast throughput receiver

T3.2 Software development for advanced statistical analysis of warm-clouds measurements and real time environmental monitoring

T3.3 Definition of the CLOUD WALKER Data Management Plan, preparation of a dedicated online repository.

WP4: Biodegradable balloon production automation

TEAM + wp4 POLITO Borsa di Ricerca grantee

T4.1 Laboratory tests of the stiffness and shear moduli and hydrophobicity of the Mater bi Balloons by varying the size

T4.2 Definition of the Mater bi Balloon production process in partnership with NOVAMONT

WP5: Prototype customized optimization for local environmental pollution and hazardous release monitoring

TEAM + wp5 POLITO Borsa di Ricerca grantee

T5.1 Design specification PCB to include CO₂, VOC and SVOC sensors

T5.2 PCB design

T5.3 Firmware development

T5.4 customized PCB lab test

WP6: Product finalization (case, software transceiver interface, balloon fast filling and user-friendly radiosonde mounting)

TEAM + wp6 POLITO Borsista di Ricerca grantee (6 months)

T6.1 Case design

T6.2 Software transceiver interface design

T6.3 Balloon fast filling

T6.4 User-friendly radiosonde mounting

WP7: Business development & Marketing

TEAM International and National Exhibition Booths preparation and management

T7.1 EGU, MMC, WMO TECO 2023

T7.2 AGU, SIRWEC 2024

General comment

- A crucial step is the balloon Mater Bi automated process of production
- **A crucial POC action is the international and national infield validation campaign. With the status of POLITO POC Team, we can still exploit the valued hospitality and advanced collaboration of academic and governmental institutions at practically zero costs. As a start-up company, this action will imply the signature of specific and costly contracts of consultancy.**

6. LABORATORY: FACILITIES, AVAILABLE EQUIPMENT AND FURTHER NECESSITIES

The design and the assembly of the platform will be carried out in the spaces of the **POLITECNICO DI TORINO**, Department of Applied Science and Technology **DISAT** <https://www.disat.polito.it/> and in the **Neuronica Lab** <https://neuronica.polito.it/en/welcome-to-neuronica-labs/> of the Department of Electronics and Telecommunication, **DET** <https://www.det.polito.it/>. The fabrication of PCB will be carried out outside.

General comment

Strategic partnership with the identified suppliers of both the printed circuits (preferably European companies) and the Mater Bi Balloons (IIT Torino-Genova, NOVAMONT Spa parent organizations as Mater-Biopolymer Srl, Mater-Biotech SPA.

7. POC DEVELOPMENT FINANCIAL NEED AND MILESTONES

The **total POC investment requested is 175.670€** for a POC plan of **18 months**, divided as follows:

- 64.500 € personnel (36.72 %)
- 36.200 € materials and components (20.61 %)
- 28.000 € external services (15.94 %)
- 28.000 € other costs (15.94 %)
- 3.000 € IP protection (1.71 %)
- 15.970 € Politecnico di Torino overhead (10 % of the above)

The main costs items for the POC plan are the following:

- **Temporary research staff.** Four research grants will be given for supporting with: Software development (13 months), Hardware and Firmware (12 months), Software transceiver interface (6 months), Biodegradable balloon production (12 months).
- **Purchase of the components.** Budget for the purchase of all materials and components for making the radiosondes, and filling the biodegradable balloon.
- **External services.** Consultancies for MaterBi manipulation and sonde mounting and casing.
- **Other costs.** Costs for exhibition booths in the main international events in Climate monitoring and Meteorological analysis (WMO TECO, SIRWEC, EGU, AGU, MMC), and for in-field demos with target customers.
- **IP and legal protection.** Costs dedicated to extending the current Italian pending patent in PCT.

POC milestones

- **M1** Prototype customized optimization (CO₂, VOC and SVOC) for local environmental pollution and hazardous release monitoring, **December 2023**
- **M2** Definition of the automated production process of the biodegradable balloons. System prototype demonstration in operational environment, **February/March 2024**
- **M3** Market validation using joint-experiments and in-field demos with target customers, **July 2024**
- **M4** First customer acquired for the different market scenarios, **July/August 2024**

The two **final milestones (M3 and M4)** corresponds to the **final objective** of the POC.

Post POC activities and investment round

After the completion of the POC that will take 18 months, the startup will be registered. The team intends to begin commercialization of the product before the end of the second year. For doing so, are expected to require 500 k€ after the POC as a first seed round in order to cover the investments for the industrialization activities and the operative costs.

During the third year, a second round of €1,3M will be required. These investments allow to: increase the sales volumes; penetrate the market to start scaling up the business; hiring new staff mainly for the commercialization; business development and customer care; carry out activities for marketing and sales.

As it's shown in the graph below, the BEP will be reached between the third and fourth year.

The financial forecasts are in accordance with the TAM SAM SOM model: based on the assumptions made, the goal of the plan is precisely to achieve the Serviceable Obtainable Market within 5 years.

The assumption for the 5th year are detailed below:

1) Science applications (Radiosonde costs 100 euro)

Estimation of usage by Italian, French, UK, major Atmosphere, Climate, Environment Research Institution: ASI, INRIM (CNR), CNRS, Max Planck Institute (Germany), MET Office (United Kingdom), NCAR, NOAA.

Each institution will use 2 clusters composed by 100 radiosondes each per year. Considering on average 10 institutions active per year:

- 2 clusters of 100 radiosondes X 10: 200.000 €
 - 5 receiver stations (one per twenty radiosondes) X 10: 25.000€
 - One-year software license X 10: 20.000 €
- TOTAL per year (all institutions): 245.000 €

2) Urban area monitoring (Radiosonde costs 160 euro)

In Italy and France, NUTS (Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics, is a hierarchical system for dividing the economic territory of the EU and the UK in three subsets) lists 19 regions at NUTS 1, 39 regions at NUTS 2, and 208 regions at NUTS 3. Assuming to sell 600 radiosondes per year per region to NUTS1 regions, 300 radiosondes per year per region to NUTS2 regions, and 60 radiosondes per year per region to NUTS3 regions, we obtain a total of:

- (NUTS1): 1.140.000 €,
 - (NUTS2): 1.170.000 €,
 - (NUTS3): 1.248.000 €
 - 150 receiver stations (three per NUTS1, two for NUTS2, one for NUTS 3 one per twenty radiosondes): 75000 €
 - One-year software license (one per region): 532.000 €
- TOTAL per year: 3.665.000 €

3) Prevention, rescue relief services (Radiosonde costs 160 euro)

In Italy there are 100 fire rescue and monitoring services (Corpo dei Vigili del Fuoco), assuming to sell on the average 20 radiosondes each per year:

- 2000 radiosondes: 320.000 €
 - 100 receiver stations per twenty radiosondes): 50000€
 - Two-years software license (one per rescue service): 200.000 €
- TOTAL per year: 570.000 €

4) Industrial safety and Decarbonization - 2050 EU Green Deal (Radiosonde cost 160 euro)

In Italy, more than 1.000 establishments (about 1700) are covered by the Seveso-III Directive. Assuming to sell 12 radiosondes each per year:

- 12000 radiosondes: 1.920.000 €
 - 1000 receiver stations (one per user): 500.000 €
 - Two-years software license (one per rescue service): 2.000.000 €
- TOTAL per year: 5.750.000 €

Appendices.

- 1) POC Development Plan GANTT, see page 15.**
- 2) POC Financial Need GANTT, see page 16.**
- 3) List of publications and relevant web links, see page 17.**
- 4) Annex 1: Expression of interest from ARPA Piemonte as separate attached file.**
- 5) Annex 2: Expression of interest from INRIM, CNR, as separate attached file.**
- 6) Annex 3: CLOUD WALKER Pitch Presentation is also included as an attachment.**
- 7) Annex 4: CLOUD WALKER overview of in-field data sets obtained during preliminary experimentations. See also slides 16-18 in Annex 3.**

WP	Tasks	Working group	Duration (months)	Feb-23	Mar-23	Apr-23	May-23	Jun-23	Jul-23	Aug-23	Sep-23	Oct-23	Nov-23	Dec-23	Jan-24	Feb-24	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24	Jul-24	
1	Business planning & Market definition			18																		
	1.1	Write the overall Business plan	TEAM + i3P + TRIN	2																		
	1.2	Define the list of actions	TEAM + i3P + TRIN	2																		
	1.3	Define the marketing strategy	TEAM + i3P + TRIN	15																		
2	In-field testing campaign - Market validation			17																		
	2.1	INT in-field testing campaign	Tordella-Randazzo-Abdunabiev + BR3	17																		
	2.2	NAT in-field testing campaign	TEAM + BR3/BR5	11																		
3	Data acquisition and management. Software further development			13																		
	3.1	SW multichannel fast throughput receiver	Tordella-Abdunabiev BR3	4																		
	3.2	SW advanced statistical analysis	Tordella-Abdunabiev BR3	11																		
	3.3	Data Management Plan	Tordella-Abdunabiev BR3	4																		
4	Biodegradable balloon production automation			12																		
	4.1	Lab tests Mater bi Balloons	Tordella-BR4	10																		
	4.2	Balloon production process	Tordella-BR4	9																		
5	Prototype customized optimization (CO2, VOC and SVOC) for local environmental pollution and hazardous release monitoring			13																		
	5.1	Spec. VOC sensor	Paser-Randazzo + BR5	3																		
	5.2	update PCB design	Paser-Randazzo + BR5	9																		
	5.3	Firmware dev.	Paser-Randazzo + BR5	8																		
	5.4	Customized PCB test	Paser-Randazzo + BR5	10																		
6	Product finalization (case, software transceiver interface, balloon fast filling and user-friendly radiosonde mounting)			9																		
	6.1	Case design	TEAM + BR6	3																		
	6.2	Software transceiver interface design	TEAM + BR6	6																		
	6.3	Balloon fast filling	TEAM + BR6	5																		
	6.4	User-friendly radiosonde mounting	TEAM + BR6	5																		
7	Business development & Marketing			12																		
	7.1	EGU, MMC, WMO TECO 2023	TEAM	8																		
	7.2	AGU SIRWEC 2024 Torino	TEAM	4																		

Appendix 2) POC Financial Need GANTT

Uses (amount in k€)	feb-23	mar-23	apr-23	mag-23	giu-23	lug-23	ago-23	set-23	ott-23	nov-23	dic-23	gen-24	feb-24	mar-24	apr-24	mag-24	giu-24	lug-24	Total (k€)
Temporary research staff research grants																			64,5
SW development	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5						19,5
Hardware and firmware	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5							18,0
SW transceiver interface											1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5			9,0
Biodegradable balloon	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,5							18,0
Purchase of goods																			36,2
Prototype components	2								2					2					6,0
MaterBi and Biodegradable balloons	3					2				2									7,0
Circuit (PCB) manufacturing				5						5						2,7			12,7
Consumables and helium	4							2,5				2			2				10,5
External services																			28,0
Consultancies for MaterBi manipulation			10					8				4							22,0
Consultancies for sonde mounting and casing												5							5,0
Brochure and Marketing materials						0,5							0,5						1,0
Other costs																			28,0
Exhibition boots							5				4				3				12,0
National in-field demos	0,5				0,5					0,5				0,5					2,0
International in-field demos						5						5				4			14,0
Patents				3															3,0
SUBTOTAL																			159,7
POLITO overhead (10%)																			15,97
TOTAL																			175,67

Appendix 3) List of publications and relevant web links

1. Paredes Quintanilla, M. E., Abdunabiev, S., Allegretti, M., Merlone, A., Musacchio, C., Pasero, E. G., ... & Canavero, F. (2021). Innovative Mini Ultralight Radioprobes to Track Lagrangian Turbulence Fluctuations within Warm Clouds: Electronic Design. *Sensors*, 21(4), 1351. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21041351>
2. Basso, T. C., Perotto, G., Musacchio, C., Merlone, A., Athanassiou, A., & Tordella, D. (2020). Evaluation of Mater Bi and Polylactic Acid as materials for biodegradable innovative mini- radiosondes to track small scale fluctuations within clouds. *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 253, 123411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2020.123411>
3. Golshan, M., Abdunabiev, S., Tomatis, M., Fraternali, F., Vanni, M., & Tordella, D. (2021). Intermittency acceleration of water droplet population dynamics inside the interfacial layer between cloudy and clear air environments. *International Journal of Multiphase Flow*, 140, 103669. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmultiphaseflow.2021.103669>
4. Fossà, L., Abdunabiev, S., Golshan, M., & Tordella, D. (2022). Microphysical timescales and local supersaturation balance at a warm cloud top boundary. *Physics of Fluids*, 34(6), 067103. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0090664>
5. Gallana, L., Abdunabiev, S., Golshan, M., & Tordella, D. (2022). Diffusion of turbulence following both stable and unstable step stratification perturbations. *Physics of Fluids*. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0090042>
6. Paredes, M., Bertoldo, S., Carosso, L., Lucianaz, C., Marchetta, E., Allegretti, M., & Savi, P. (2019). Propagation measurements for a LoRa network in an urban environment. *Journal of Electromagnetic Waves and Applications*, 33(15), 2022-2036. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09205071.2019.1661287>
7. Bui, T. D., Basso, T. C., Bertoldo, S., & Attanasio, C. (2018, October). Trajectory reconstruction of balloon radiosondes for tracking air fluctuations inside warm clouds. In *2018 IEEE SENSORS* (pp. 1- 4). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSENS.2018.8589783>
8. Paredes, M., Bertoldo, S., Lucianaz, C., & Allegretti, M. (2018, April). Ultra-light disposable radio probes for atmospheric monitoring. In *EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts* (p. 1389). <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2018EGUGA..20.1389P/abstract>
9. Paredes, M., Abdunabiev, S., Allegretti, M., Perona, G., Tordella, D., Pasero, E., ... & Musacchio, C. (2020, May). Progress on the development of innovative, floating, biodegradable radio-probes for atmospheric monitoring inside warm clouds. In *EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts* (p. 22374). <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2020EGUGA..2222374P/abstract>
10. G. Cirrincione, G. Ciravegna, P. Barbiero, V. Randazzo and E. Pasero, "The GH-EXIN neural network for hierarchical clustering", in *Neural Networks*, 121, 2020, pp. 57-73 Elsevier Ltd.

11. G. Cirrincione, V. Randazzo, E. Pasero, "The Growing Curvilinear Component Analysis (GCCA) neural network", in Neural Networks, 103, 2018, pp. 108-117, Elsevier Ltd.
12. V. Randazzo, J. Ferretti and E. Pasero, "A Wearable Smart Device to Monitor Multiple Vital Parameters – VITAL ECG", in Electronics, 9(2), 2020, MDPI.
13. V. Randazzo, G. Cirrincione and E. Pasero, "A new unsupervised neural approach to stationary and non-stationary data analysis", in Advances in Data Science: Methodologies and Applications, 2021, pp. 125-145, Springer, Cham.
14. A. Paviglianiti, V. Randazzo, S. Villata, G. Cirrincione and E. Pasero, "A comparison of Deep Learning techniques for Arterial Blood Pressure prediction", in Cognitive Computation, 2021, pp. 1-22, Springer.

List and links to promotional material already available (ex. video, websites, etc)

www.complete-h2020network.eu, for the 18th of July we can add a few movies of the in-field experiments run up to know.

Experiments and tests published on the COMPLETE website:

- <https://www.complete-h2020network.eu/news/field-radiosonde-experiment-astronomical-observatory-saint-barthelemy-located-lignan-italy>
- <https://www.complete-h2020network.eu/news/testing-five-radioprobes-inrim-politecnico-di-torino-group>
- <https://www.complete-h2020network.eu/news/testing-radioprobe-inrim-politecnico-di-torino-group>
- <https://www.complete-h2020network.eu/news/recent-experiment-done-politrecnico-di-torino>
- <https://www.complete-h2020network.eu/news/latest-experiment-first-prototypes-radio-probe>
- <https://www.complete-h2020network.eu/news/latest-experiment-envisens-and-politecnico-groups>